

HERBAL TREATMENT FOR DIABETES MELLITUS

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Fatima Qamarfatimamudassar2009@hotmail.com**Abstract**

The existence of chronic hyperglycemia is characterized by metabolic disorder is known as diabetes or diabetes mellitus. It may be a diabetes mellitus type1 (immune mediated), diabetes mellitus type2 (insulin resistance), gestational diabetes and others (genetic flaw, environment, infection and certain drugs). Diabetes mellitus is diagnoses by different approach in individuals like oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), fasting blood glucose test (FBG), and random blood glucose test (RBG) and hemoglobin A1c test (HbA1c).

Diabetes mellitus increase the risk of severe complications in patients which suffer from diabetes mellitus such as autonomic neuropathy, retinopathy, and diabetic foot, impairment of immune system, nephropathy, periodontal disease and cardiovascular diseases. There are many medication like sulfonylureas, meglitindes/ glinides, biguanides,

dipeptidyl peptidase- 4 inhibitors but in this thesis we will study and focus on herbal medications used to treat diabetes mellitus.

INTRODUCTION

DIABETES MELLITUS

Defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both causes hyperglycemia that result metabolic disorder that called diabetes or diabetes mellitus. Dysfunction, long term damage and failure of different organ specially heart, kidney, blood vessels, nerves and eye is associated with chronic hyperglycemia of diabetes.(Alam, Asghar, Azmi, & Malik, 2014) (Pang et al., 2019)

In the development of diabetes several pathogen process are involved. Due to destruction of beta cell of pancreas insulin deficiency and abnormalities occurs that result in insulin resistance. Deficient action of insulin on target tissues abnormalities of carbohydrate, fats and protein metabolism is occur. (Blair, 2016)

Weight loss, polydipsia, polyphagia, and polyurea are marked symptoms of hyperglycemia. Hyperglycemia with ketoacidosis or nonketotic hyperosmolar syndrome is life threatening consequences of uncontrolled diabetes.(Bastaki, 2005)

Peripheral neuropathy with risk of foot ulcers, autonomic neuropathy causing gastrointestinal, retinopathy with potential loss of vision, renal failure, genitourinary, cardiovascular symptoms and sexual dysfunction are long term complication of diabetes. Cerebrovascular diseases, atherosclerotic cardiovascular are incidence of patient with diabetes. In patient with diabetes hypertension and abnormalities of lipoprotein metabolism are also found.

Genetic defects, gestational hormonal environment, certain drugs and other infections are also related with diabetes.

TYPES OF DIABETES MELLITUS:

Diabetes has many types that are as follows:

TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS:

Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) and Juvenile diabetes are other name of type 1 diabetes. This type of diabetes occurs in childhood and early adulthood. It is a lifelong autoimmune condition. In this glucose level is not metabolize because insulin is not produce. In this type body destroys the beta cell in the pancreas which are responsible for secrete insulin and also attack its own immune system.(Katsarou et al., 2017)

Diabetes ketoacidosis is more prevalence in type 1 diabetes. Insulin secretion is maintained in adult to prevent ketoacidosis that indicate as latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA).

TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS:

Non insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM) and adult onset diabetes are other name of type 2 diabetes. It occurs in 85 to 90 % people with diabetes. Combination of some degree of insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency is characterized by type 2 diabetes. In this type insulin is still produce by body but it is not enough and not works well to maintain blood glucose level in healthy range. By increased hepatic glucose production, lipolysis and free fatty acid production and decreased skeletal muscle uptake of glucose insulin resistance is manifested.(DeFronzo et al., 2015)

PREDIABETES:

Blood glucose level is higher than normal that result pre diabetes but it is not enough to diagnose diabetes. It has higher risk of developing type 2 diabetes, strokes and heart diseases. In this fasting blood glucose level is 100 milligram per deciliter or more and less than 126 milligram per deciliter for diabetes. 5.7 % to 6.5 % hemoglobin A1C level for pre

diabetes and greater than 6.5% hemoglobin A1C level for diabetes. Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) or impaired fasting glucose (IFG) is also referred as pre diabetes.(Khetan & Rajagopalan, 2018)

GESTATIONAL DIABETES:

During pregnancy gestational diabetes is develop in women. Sometime after baby is born this type of diabetes is go away. 3 to 9 percent of pregnancies are affected by gestational diabetes. It is usually diagnose in third trimester of pregnancy. Later in life you have greater chance of developing type 2 diabetes if you have gestational diabetes.(McIntyre et al., 2019)

OTHER SPECIFIC TYPES:

There are many kinds of diabetes mellitus whose causes are known and they are classified in another group referred as other specific types. The people which are included in this classifications are the people which have genetic flaws of their beta cell function and this type of diabetes are also called as MODY or maturity onset diabetes in youth or maybe they have flaws in their action of insulin and maybe they have disease of pancreas specially exocrine pancreas which include pancreatitis and cystic fibrosis.(Kota, Meher, Jammula, Kota, & Modi, 2012) This classification also has people which have endocrinopathies for example acromegaly and it also includes people who take drugs, chemicals or may be infected by infections whose pancreases don't work properly. Altogether less than 10% of the cases of diabetes mellitus are fall in to this category.

ENDOCRINE PANCREAS:

Diabetes is a disorder of pancreas. In adult human endocrine pancreas contain almost one million islets of langerhans that are spread all over the pancreatic gland. In the islets slightly four hormone producing cells are existent.(Bakhti, Böttcher, & Lickert, 2019)

SECRETORY PRODUCT AND CELLS OF THE PANCREATIC ISLETS:**Alpha cell:**

Hormone glucagon is produce by alpha cells as well as prepares almost 20 % of each islet. In blood glucose regulation glucagon plays a significant role.(Campbell & Newgard, 2021)

Beta cell:

Hormone insulin is produce by beta cells as well as prepares almost 75% of each islet. Release of insulin is stimulated by exalted blood glucose levels.

Delta cell:

Peptide hormone somatostatin is produce by delta cells as well as prepares almost 4 % of the islet cell. Hypothalamus is also secreting somatostatin. It is an inhibiting hormone. Glucagon and insulin release is inhibit by the pancreatic somatostatin.

Pancreatic polypeptide (pp) cell:

Pancreatic polypeptide hormone is produce by pp cell as well as prepares almost 1 % of the islet cell. After meal pancreatic polypeptide is rapidly secrete but remain exalted for 4 to 6 hours in human. Metabolism, GI motility and food intake has effect by pancreatic polypeptide.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:**TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS:**

Pancreas has beta cells called islets of langerhans these are insulin secreting beta cells so when the destruction of these cells occurs and infiltration of lymphatic cells occurs type diabetes mellitus results. Normal blood glucose level are not regulated because when the mass of beta cell decreases ultimately secretion of insulin also decrease and their result stage come when no insulin is present to fulfill the needs of normal blood glucose level. Almost 80 to 90 % of the beta cells are dementia and a condition recalled hyperglycemia

or diabetes finally diagnosed to the patient. In this patient need a reversible supply of insulin to prevent any further accidental emergency condition and to normalize liquid and protein metabolism.(Strazzabosco, Fabris, & Spirli, 2005)

The pathophysiology of diabetes mellitus type 1 is currently based on autoimmunity factor so when a patient is susceptible to autoimmune disorder or any viral infection it can stimulate the formation of antibodies in our body against the viral protein present in our body. It will stimulate autoimmune response against anti genetically determinant and likewise molecules of beta cells. Majority of the patient suffering from type 1 approximately 85 have regulating islet cells antibodies and most of them also have antibodies of anti insulin which can be detect before patient get insulin therapy. There is an enzyme available in beta cell of pancreas called as glutamic acid decarboxylase or GAD so the antibodies of islet cell work against these enzymes most commonly. Diabetes mellitus type 1 is widely spread in patient who already has weak immune system and has diseases like Addison disease, hashimoto thyroiditis and grave diseases.

TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS:

Pancreatic beta cells are responsible to secrete inadequate insulin and type 2 diabetes mellitus is based on the combination of peripheral insulin resistance. Increased level of free fatty acid and inflammatory mediators like cytokine in plasma is due to the insulin resistance and which causes reduced in transport of glucose in muscle cells. It ultimately results in increased production of hepatic glucose and elevated damage of fat.

We cannot underestimate the role of over production of glucagon. In type 2 diabetes islet paracrinopathy has a relationship which is reciprocal between the insulin secreting beta cells and glucagon secreting alpha cells. This relationship is totally not available which

ultimately result in over production of glucagon and also get causes over production of glucose.

It is important for diabetes mellitus type 2 that the both inappropriate insulin secretion and insulin resistance should present. For example we can see that all of the people who are overweight they may suspected to insulin resistance but for the case of diabetes, diabetes only produce in those individuals who cannot increased their secretion of insulin sufficiently so they can not compensate with their insulin resistance.

For the people who have diabetes mellitus since a long period of time. The atrophy of pancreas may happen. There is sampling study by philippe which comprises of computed tomography (ct scan), test result of glucagon stimulation and fecal elastase this ensures the lesser volume of pancreas in people who have a 15 year history of diabetes mellitus. The test conducted their also allobrate the deficiency in the exocrine functions of the patient who have diabetes for long period of time.

Beta cell dysfunction:

The most prime factor is beta cell dysfunction in which there is a studied is conducted in adults at Bacha et al this study ensures that why the adults are being stress and why the ratio of adults are increasing by being stress. All the necessary stages of insulin resistance are not followed by beta cell dysfunction because it is produce late in therapeutic process. For more pronounce and efficient therapy there are more better option which have been evolving which addresses the beta cell pathology and all the focus on singular insulin resistance have been changed.

Insulin resistance:

Postprandial levels of blood glucose at once start elevating when there is a proceed start from normal to abnormal glucose tolerance. Ultimately there is a failure in the repression

of hepatic gluconeogenesis because fasting hyperglycemia produce. When high calorie diet is taken or when the physical inactivity is perform insulin resistance is begin induce it ultimately elevate the level of glucagon and level of GIP which also follow intolerance of glucose. Postprandial glucagon like peptide GLP remains unchanged.

Genomic factors:

Identification of genetic variants which are related to the insulin resistance and beta cell function have been studied by genome wide association and they mostly studies about single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The chance of type 2 diabetes has been elevated because of these SNPs and the most prominent subgroup is giving as follows:

1. Metabolism of fat is not regulated properly.
2. Release of serum glucose is stop.
3. Unsaturated fatty acid's metabolism change completely.
4. Early insulin release which is stimulated by glucose is reduced.
5. Insulin secretion is decreased and processing of insulin is impaired due to the lesser response of beta cell.
6. Resistance of insulin is increase and concentration of adipose tissue is also increase.

CLINICAL PRESENTATION OF DIABETES MELLITUS:

TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS:

HISTORY:

Polyphagia, polyurea, polydipsia, blurred vision, candidiasis, cramps, constipation, fatigue and weight loss are the symptoms of type 1 diabetes. (Roche, Menon, Gill, & Hoey, 2005)

Due to osmotic diuresis polyurea occur. In young children onset of diabetes is indicate by severe nocturnal enuresis which is secondary to polyurea. Due to the muscle wasting from

catabolic state of insulin deficiency, hypovolemia and hypokalemia that result fatigue and weakness. Electrolyte imbalance caused muscle cramps. Hyperosmolar state on the lens and vitreous humor that result blurred vision. Osmotic swelling of the lens is caused by glucose and its metabolites. Several days to several weeks we can trace the symptoms at the time of clinical presentation. Started months or even year beta cell destruction can occur. Sudden onset of symptomatic disease. Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is not usually occurring with type 1 diabetes, it can be occur due to the stress of illness or surgery.

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Finding is usually normal in physical examination. Sign of dehydration, hypotension, and Kussmaul respiration in patient with diabetes ketoacidosis and altered mental status in some cases. Macrovascular and microvascular complications should be examined after every 3 months. Monofilament testing for peripheral neuropathy and fundoscopic examination for retinopathy are also tests. (Thomas Byrd, 2005)

DIABETES FOCUSED EXAMINATION:

Assessment of vital signs, limited vascular and neurologic examinations, fundoscopic examination and foot examination are included. (Antonelli et al., 2013)

Assessment of vital signs:

When patients have autonomic neuropathy and established diabetes that result in orthostatic hypotension. The presence of autonomic neuropathy is suggested by orthostatic vital signs. Pulses are measured which is essential for patients, in autonomic neuropathy relative tachycardia are typical findings. Immediately considered DKA if respiratory rate and pattern suggest Kussmaul respiration and ordered some appropriate tests.

Funduscopy examination:

Retina should be examined in funduscopy examination. Visualize both macula and optic disc. Patient should be referring to ophthalmologist if exudates and hemorrhages are seen.

Foot examination:

Posterior tibialis pulses and dorsalis will be palpated. It is important in patient with foot infection, healing can be delay due to poor lower extremity blood flow and risk of amputation is increased. Patient should care their foot (daily foot examination). It is very necessary for prevention foot ulcer and lower extremity amputation.

COMPLICATIONS:**Infections:**

Morbidity and mortality is caused by infection in patient with diabetes. Metabolic derangement can be precipitate by infection.

Micro vascular and macro vascular diseases in patient who have long standing diabetes which result poor tissue perfusion and risk of infection is increased. Various type of the infection increased the risk of diabetes. Urinary tract and skin are the most common sites. In dermatologic infection cellulitis, oral or genital candidal infections, staphylococcal follicular skin infection and superficial fungal infection are more common which increased the risk of diabetes. Greater frequency of lower urinary tract infection and acute pyelonephritis are seen.

Ophthalmologic complications:

Retina, lens and vitreous are affecting by the diabetes and also visual symptoms occur. Due to changes in blood glucose concentration lens change their shape and visual burning may develop acutely and this effect is caused by osmotic fluxes of water inside

and outside the lens. Senile cataracts are developing in patient with diabetes at younger age. Snowflake or metabolic cataract may be developing in patient with type 1 diabetes. The most common complication of diabetes mellitus is diabetic retinopathy. Blindness is the leading cause of diabetic retinopathy.

Diabetic nephropathy:

Evidence of nephropathy is developing in 20 to 30 % patient with type 1 diabetes. Decline in renal function is caused by elevated blood pressure. Acute renal failure is precipitate by use contrast media in patient with diabetic nephropathy.

Macro vascular complications:

Atherosclerosis is accelerated in patient with diabetes. Small arteries of heart, lower extremity, brain and kidney are mostly affected. At younger age coronary atherosclerosis often occur and also risk of the ischemic heart diseases increased. Gangrene is predisposed by the severe atherosclerosis of iliofemoral and smaller arteries of lower legs. Diabetic peripheral vascular diseases are characterize by ischemia of single toe and ischemic area on the heel.

Risk factors for macro vascular diseases:

In patient with diabetes macro vascular diseases is leading cause of death. Almost 65 to 75 % of death in this type of group. Risk of myocardial infarction (4 fold in women and 2 fold in men) is increasing.

TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS:

HISTORY:

Polyuria, polydipsia, polyphagia, weight loss are the classical symptoms of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Blurred vision, yeast infection, lower extremity paresthesias and particular

balanitis in men are the other common symptoms. At the time of diagnosis in patient with diabetes has diabetes for 4 to 7 years.

DAWN PHENOMENON:

At the end of night blood glucose is increase over 20 milligram per deciliter which is common in type 2 diabetes. Glucose level and HbA1c level is increased in dawn phenomenon.

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION:

Findings of physical examination are unrevealing. The possible findings are hypertension, obesity, eye hemorrhage, exudates and candida infection, muscle atrophy, ulcers.

DIABETES FOCUSED EXAMINATION:

Foot examination, vascular and neurologic examination, vital sign and fundoscopic examination are included in diabetes focused examination.

Assessment of vital signs:

The important part of diabetes management is measurement of vital sign, height, weight, waist and hip circumferences. Hypertension will be disclosed by measuring blood pressure. When patient have autonomic neuropathy and established diabetes that result in orthostatic hypotension. The presence of autonomic neuropathy is suggested by orthostatic vital sign. Diabetic ketoacidosis are considered immediately if respiratory rate and pattern suggest the kussmaul respiration.

Fundoscopic examination:

Retina should be examined in fundoscopic examination. Visualize both macula and optic disc. Patient should refer to ophthalmologist if exudates and hemorrhages are seen. Diabetic retinopathy is depending on period of diabetes and level of glycemic control

maintained. Delayed diagnosis in type 2 diabetes, at the time of diagnosis 20 % patient has retinopathy.

Foot examination:

Posterior tibialis pulses and dorsalis pedis will palpate and noted their presence and absence. It is important in patient which have foot infection, healing can be slow due to poor lower extremity blood flow and risk of amputation is increased. To prevent foot ulcers and lower extremity amputation patient should care their foot by daily foot examination.

COMPLICATION:

SHORT TERM COMPLICATIONS:

Hypoglycemia:

It is define as the low blood glucose level in body. It is occurring especially when patient with diabetes take insulin and anti diabetic agents. Hypoglycemia is also cause by other drug like aspirin and too much alcohol. Patient should carry glucagon with them when they have taken insulin. Glucagon starts the process in body that increases the blood glucose level. Confusion, whiteness of skin, rapid heartbeat, sleepiness, sweating, numbness of fingers, lips and toes are the symptoms of hypoglycemia.(Kalra et al., 2013)

Hyperosmolar hyperglycemic nonketotic syndrome:

It is a rare syndrome when you don't treat it, it can cause death. In this syndrome blood glucose level is too elevated. It is occur in patient which is sick and elderly people. Blood glucose level is always checking regularly to avoid the hyperosmolar hyperglycemia nonketotic syndrome.

LONG TERM COMPLICATION:

To avoid long term complication you have maintained their blood glucose level, and take medications and also do some physical activity.

Both tiny and large blood vessels are damage by high blood glucose level. Micro vascular complication occurs by damage in tiny blood vessels and macro vascular complication occurs by damage in large vessels.(Nathan, 1993)

Micro vascular complications:

By high blood glucose level small vessels are damage which not deliver the blood and cause many problems.

Eye: Retinopathy and cataract are cause by high blood glucose level which can cause loss of vision.

Kidney: Dialysis, kidney transplant and impaired kidney function are cause when you not treat kidney disease. Kidney failure is caused by uncontrolled diabetes. Microalbuminuria should be test every year to prevent diabetic nephropathy.

Nerve: Diabetes causes the nerve damage which is known as diabetic neuropathy. Diabetic neuropathy has various forms like proximal, peripheral, focal and autonomic. The most common form of nerve damage is diabetic peripheral neuropathy (in this hands and feet is affect).

Macro vascular complications:

Large blood vessel is damage by type 2 diabetes. Stroke, heart attack and vessel blockage in the legs are caused by plaque buildup in the vessels. Maintained the uncontrolled diabetes to prevent heart diseases and stroke.

ETIOLOGY:**TYPE 1 DIABETES MELLITUS:**

Due to the autoimmune destruction of the beta cells of pancreas that results in type 1 diabetes. Environmental component and genetic predisposition are involved in this. (Bushman, 2009)

Genetic factors:

Type 1 diabetes genetic aspect is complex. In type 1 diabetes 5 to 6% concordance in dizygotic twins. Risk of developing diseases is 2 to 3% in children whose mother are diabetes mellitus type 1. Whereas 5 to 6 % whose father are diabetic patient. Risk of disease is 30% if both parents are diabetic patient. Several loci which are correlate with type 1 diabetes that are studied by genome wide association. Autoimmune diseases also strongly correlate with genomic region.

Pre proinsulin peptide is encoded by insulin gene INS which is contiguous with a variable number of tandem repeat VNTR. Susceptibility of diabetes mellitus type 1 is promoted by VNTR alleles by effect on insulin gene transcription. Diabetes mellitus type 1 is also reported by other gene like PTPN22 which produce LYP, which is a T cell kinase signaling negative regulator and CTLA4 which are important in T cell activation.

Environmental factors:

Virus (rubella, mumps, coxsackievirus, and enterovirus), cytotoxin, exposure to cow milk in infant and toxic chemical can cause the destruction of beta cells. The child of age of 12

month is associated with the appearance of diabetes which is cause by enterovirus, while in age of before 3 months is associated with diabetes which is cause by exposure of cow milk that are studied by Lempainen et al.

The autoimmunity islet and progression of diabetes mellitus type 1 are associated with childhood which is not taken vitamin D and 25 hydroxyvitamin level that are studied by simpson et al.

Risk of diabetes mellitus type 1 is also increase when patient have upper respiratory tract infection.

TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS:

The interaction of genetic and environmental factor that cause the diabetes mellitus type 2. Dibetogenic lifestyle like obesity, inadequate caloric consumption and excessive caloric intake is also cause type 2diabetes.

Risk of diabetes is also increase by excess weight, pre hypertension and hypertension.

Diabetes mellitus type 2 is developing in patient almost 90 % which are obese.

Major risk factors:

Diabetes mellitus type 2 has major risk factor which is giving below:

1. Desirable body weight is increased by 120%.
2. Above 45 year age is develop high risk of diabetes.
3. Impaired fasting glucose and impaired glucose tolerance history.
4. When patient have dyslipidemia and hypertension.
5. Family history of diabetes mellitus type 2.
6. When patient have polycystic ovarian syndrome.

Genetic influence:

Diabetes mellitus type 2 genetics is complex and not understood. Insulin resistance and pancreatic beta cells failure is caused by multiple genes. The risk of diabetes mellitus type 2 is increased which is correlated by genetic variants that studied by genome wide association.

Genetic flaws are associated with diabetes like maturity onset diabetes of youth. Variety of flaw in beta cell functions is understood in 2 to 5% individual with diabetes mellitus type 2. Severe mitochondrial disorder can also cause diabetes like lactic acidosis, mitochondrial encephalomyopathy and stroke like episode.

Depression:

Diabetes mellitus type 2 is also developing by depression. 1.25 risk in women which is using antidepressant and 1.17 risk in women which have depressed mood that studied by Pan et al. By weight gain and altering the glucose homeostasis antidepressant increase the risk of diabetes.

Schizophrenia:

Type 2 diabetes mellitus also caused by schizophrenia. The possible mechanism is dysfunctional signaling is involve protein kinase B (Akt). Impaired regulation of diabetes and blood glucose is associated by Akt flaws. Risk of diabetes mellitus type 2 is also increase by antipsychotic drugs.

DIAGNOSIS:

FASTING PLASMA GLUCOSE TEST (FPG):

Diabetes is screening by fasting plasma glucose test. After at least 8 hour fasting and no eating, the level of blood glucose is measure that refer fasting plasma glucose test. Below 100 mg/dl is the normal value of FPG. When blood glucose level are higher than 100 milligram per deciliter and below 126 milligram per deciliter that cause pre diabetes but

patient have not yet diabetes. If the blood glucose level is higher than 126 milligram per deciliter then patient diagnose with diabetes. On subsequent day this test can be repeating for proper diagnosis.(Trujillo, Vigo, Reichelt, Duncan, & Schmidt, 2014)

RANDOM BLOOD GLUCOSE TEST (RBG):

At random time of a day blood glucose level is measure. If the blood glucose level is 200 milligram per deciliter and greater than 200 milligram per deciliter then patient diagnose with diabetes.(Bowen, Xuan, Lingvay, & Halm, 2015)

ORAL GLUCOSE TOLERANCE TEST (OGTT):

After at least 8 hour fasting and no eating, the level of blood glucose is measure then after 2 hour you can drink fluid which is containing 75 gm of glucose then measure blood glucose level. When the blood glucose level are 140 to 199 milligram per deciliter after drink fluid then patient diagnose as pre diabetic and IGT. If the blood glucose level is 200 milligram per deciliter and greater than 200 milligram per deciliter then patient diagnose as diabetic. (Bartoli, Fra, & Schianca, 2011)

HbA1c:

Glycated haemoglobin is another name of HbA1c. When red blood cell within protein carries the oxygen in all over the body and accompanied with glucose it become a glycated. Average plasma glucose concentration is identifying by HbA1c. Diagnostic guidelines of diabetes are as follows:

1. When HbA1c value is less than 6.0 percent then patient have no diabetes.
2. When the HbA1c value lies in between 6.0 to 6.4 percent then patient is pre diabetic.
3. When the HbA1c value is 6.5 percent and greater than 6.5 percent then patient diagnose with diabetes.

PHARMACOLOGICAL TREATMENT:

Patient must be rely on insulin to management of hyperglycemia and avoid ketoacidosis in diabetes mellitus type 1. The HbA1c level should be maintained within the normal range. To prevent the fluctuation in glucose and maintained blood glucose level within the normal range, it is goal of insulin therapy. (Connolly & Lang, 2014)

To avoid long term complication and maintained blood glucose level within the normal range, it is a goal of diabetes mellitus 2. In diabetes mellitus type2, decrease insulin resistance and hyperglycemia by dietary modification, weight loss and exercise in some patient and also some patient require anti diabetic agents.

INSULIN PREPARATION:

Rapid, short, intermediate and long acting are the classification of insulin preparation.

Regular insulin:

Aspart insulin, lispro and glulisine are characterized as rapid acting insulin. This insulin are like crystals and has solubilizing properties alternation in the amino acid arrangement of regular insulin forms rapid an acting insulin analogs. By administering rapid acting insulin we actually check the meal time release of insulin and also control this prandial effect of glucose and it is very help full in some situation where we need to correct the rapid elevation of glucose. These are use in combination with longer acting insulin that gives you fasting glucose control. Time of administration of regular insulin is 30 minutes before the meal and subcutaneously and rapid acting insulin are injected 15 minutes prior to meal and may be after 15 to 20 minutes after you eat meal. In external insulin pump mostly rapid acting insulin suspensions are used and they also convenient for administration via IV but regular insulin is not appropriate in case of IV.

Neutral protamine hagedorn (NPH):(Owens, 2011)

In regular insulin when we add protamine and zinc and intermediate acting insulin is produce called neutral protamine hagedorn (NPH). These combinations produce less soluble complex which consequences are time taken absorption and delay duration of action.

In type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus NPH insulin is usually administered for fasting control but in addition to this it is also giving with short acting or rapid acting insulin to control the meal time.

Insulin glargine:

This insulin shows very moderate onset of action as compared to NPH insulin without any peak an also the hypoglycemic effect is very prolong because this insulin secretes for longer time period. All the insulin detemir, insulin degludec and insulin glargine are giving with NPH insulin helpful in controlling basal and it should only be given subcutaneously. Degludec insulin has an ability to be in solution and release slowly for longer period of time and also posses the longest half life of all long acting insulin's. Symptoms serious adverse effects like hypoglycemia also occur. Others side effect we can see gain of weight, irritation at site of local injection and lipodystrophy which can be reduce by the circulation at site of injection and in case of renal insufficiency one should need to lower the dose of insulin.

Synthetic amylin analogues/ amylinomimetic:

When we take a food this hormone amylin is released along with insulin from beta cells. Due to which gastric emptying rate are also decreases with post prandial decreased. Before meal pramlintide injection are need to be given subcutaneously. Patient type 1 and type 2 diabetes mellitus are suppose to take pramlintide has an additive in meal time insulin therapy.

ORAL AGENTS:

Diabetes mellitus type 2 is not controlled by diet then the patient takes oral agents such as:

Sulfonylureas:(Luna & Feinglos, 2001)

Sulfonylurea are characterize into group called insulin secretagogues. They are supposed to improve the release of insulin from the beta cell of pancreas. These are the drugs which are generally used clinically. These are the second generation drugs which includes glimepiride, glyburide and glipizide. Depolarization occurs when sulfonylureas inhibit calcium channels, ATP sensitive potassium channels, and calcium influx and exocytosis of insulin. In further more these sulfonylureas have also an ability to decrease the formation of hepatic glucose and elevate the sensitivity of peripheral insulin. Side effect which shown usually are gain of weight, increase of insulin and hypoglycemia and they also cause renal and hepatic insufficiency so it use with cautions.

Meglitinides/ Glinides:

They posses same activity as sulfonylureas with in addition they also have swift onset of action and less duration of action. The drugs include in these are repaglinide and nateglinide. They also regulate the release of insulin. They are very useful in for the release of insulin soon after the patient has taken the meal that is why they classify into postprandial regulators of glucose but something in caution that these glinides should not be given with sulfonylureas because then the mechanism will overlap or subside and increase the risk of hyperglycemia occur.

Biguanides:

Biguanides have only one drug which is metformin and it is usually characterize into insulin sensitizers. Target tissues use this drug by elevating uptake of glucose and

reducing resistance of insulin. In contrary with sulfonylureas these biguanides does not possess the ability of secretion of insulin there for the side effect of hypoglycemia is far away. Polycystic ovarian syndrome can also be treated with metformin because it reduces the resistance of insulin. Mechanism of action of metformin is basically reduction in gluconeogenesis of liver. This drug also shows intestinal absorption of sugars but also has beneficial side like it may cause weight loss because of the loss of appetite. This is the drug of choice for type 2 diabetes mellitus. We can use this drug alone or may be in combination with other insulin or oral diabetic agent but in this case hypoglycemia can be cause because we are taking medicine in combination with insulin or insulin secretagogues. The adverse effect which this drug is reported are diarrhea, vomiting, nausea, and obviously this drug is not indicated when patient has already dysfunction of kidney because in that case electric acidosis can occur but if we use for a very long time deficiency of vitamin b12 is caused.

Alpha glucosidase inhibitors:

In the treatment of diabetes 2 miglitol and acarbose these 2 agents are widely utilize. Breakdown of carbohydrates occurred by the help of alpha glucosidase in to simple sugars and other kind of glucose after that it will be absorb. Alpha glucosidase enzymes are reversibly blocked by miglitol and acarbose. The digestion of carbohydrate become prolong if in the beginning of meal we take this drug. As consequence decrease in postprandial level of glucose occurs so these drugs cannot regulate the release of insulin or insulin sensitivity. These drugs are not responsible for hyperglycemia even when it is use orally or signally. The most emerging side effect is abdominal pain, flatulence, and loose motion.

Dipeptidyl peptidase- 4 (DPP- 4) inhibitors:

Type 2 diabetes mellitus can also be treated by class of drugs called as DPP-4 inhibitors which include medicine like sitagliptin, saxagliptin, alogliptin, and linagliptin. DPP-4 enzyme has a role in the inhibition of incretin hormone such as GLP-1. These drugs blocked the activity of this hormone. As a result it delayed the activity of incretin hormone and the release of insulin also increases in response to meals. And the reduction in inadequate secretion of glucagon occurs. In monotherapy DPP-4 inhibitor can be utilize but in combination it is also be used like in combination with sulfonylurea and metformin or insulin. Basically these drugs can be tolerated and common side effects can be headache and nasopharyngitis and in frequently pancreatitis can also be cause by taking DPP-4 inhibitor.

HERBAL TREATMENT FOR DIABETES:

To avoid high risk of diabetes mellitus people use most common herbs and spices which have blood glucose lowering properties.(Modak, Dixit, Londhe, Ghaskadbi, & Devasagayam, 2007)

HOLY BASIL (OCIMUM SANCTUM):

Holy basil is an herb which grows in tropical areas every year. It is a branched herb which is 18 inches tall. It is commonly known as tulsi, holy basil and tulasi. It has also medicinal a value along side with religious importance and it is used in ayurvedic therapy. It also put an impact on blood sugar and fasting blood sugar. Immunological disorders like asthma and some kind of allergies can also be managed by using these herbs. The juice which its leaf has play important role in reducing the sugar level in the blood and fight against diabetic.(Singh & Chaudhuri, 2018)

COCCINIA INDICA:

Ivy gourd is another name of coccinia indica. They are cultivated wild across the Indian subcontinent. Insulin mimetic properties are found in this herb. Blood glucose level should be regulating by coccinia indica and prevent from diabetes mellitus. It also have antioxidant, antiulcer, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, expectorant properties. (Hussain, Wahab, Zarin, & Hussain, 2010)

SILK COTTON TREE (CEIBA PENTANDRA):

Sumauma, kapok tree and kankantri are the other name of silk cotton tree. Silk cotton tree have hypoglycemic effect. To treat type 2 diabetes and headache ceiba pentandra bark have been used as aphrodisiac and diuretic. Experimental studies has be done it was found that ceiba pentandra also had anti diabetic activity it was capable to produce hyperglycemia in streptozotocin induced diabetes mellitus type 2 rats and it is also used as an anti diabetic therapy for new orally active agents.(Howe, 1906)

CURRY LEAVES (MURRAYA KOENIGII):

It belongs to the family rutaceae and it is a tropical and subtropical tree. It is commonly known as sweet neem leave and curry leaves. Blood glucose level should be reducing by curry leave by use twice in a day. For regular diet it is a good herb. By experimental studies on extract of curry leave it found that curry leaves has hypoglycemic effect through higher insulin secretion and glycogenesis enhancement. It is done on alloxan induced diabetic rat. They also regulated biochemical ratio which are correlate with diabetes mellitus.(Bhandari, 2012)

BIOPHYTUM SENSITIVUM:

Life plant is another name of biophytum sensitivum and it's belonging to the family oxalidaceae. Pectin, essential oil, terpenes, flavonoids, amino acids, polysaccharides, and

steroids are present in extract of biophytum sensitivum. Experimental study which is done in normal and steptozotonic nicotinamide induced diabetic rats, in this they administered the 200 milligram per kilogram of plant for 28 days orally, it shows that within 28 days it can start lowering the blood glucose level and glycosylated haemoglobin and also it can be increases the liver glycogen, total hemoglobin and plasma insulin in diabetic rats. (Sakthivel & Guruvayoorappan, 2012)

BARLERIA PRIONITIS:

It is commonly known as porcupine flower. Experimental studies are done in normal and alloxan induced diabetic rats. In these studies they administered the 200 milligram per kilogram of alcoholic extract of this leaf for 14 days and after 14 day they found that it significantly decreases the blood glucose level and glycosylated haemoglobin levels and also prevent from weight loss.(Banerjee, Banerjee, Jha, & Bose, 2021)

INDIAN GOOSEBERRY (EUGENIA JAMBOLANA):

Jaman, java plum, black plum and jamun is a common name of Indian gooseberry. It is 50 to 100ft tall herb and it has germinating flowers and purple black eatable berries. The ingredients like resin, Gallic acid and tannin have juicy and fruity pulp. These ingredients give reducing blood sugar effect that is hypoglycemic effect and also has antioxidant characteristic. All of the parts can be utilized for their medicinal effect and also used in alternative medicines. The bark it contained has anti inflammatory properties and also used for anemia wide spread in India. The seed it contained and bark has also anti diabetic properties and also decreases the level of blood sugar.

SHATTERSTONE (PHYLLANTHUS NIRURI/ AMARUS):

Gulf leaf flower, bahupatra or gale of wind, child picks a back and shatterstone is a common name. It is annually producing herb from the genus phyllanthus and it has more

than 700 species. Experimental studies done on animals prove that the seeds and the leaf of aqueous extract of this species *Phyllanthus amarus* are proved to decrease the insulin effect and also useful in improving insulin resistance diabetes and another studies also done on aqueous extract of *Phyllanthus niruri* manifest low effect on blood glucose in non insulin independent patient. The extract of this species lower the blood sugar also decrease postprandial rise in blood glucose. They also protect liver and also have anti bacterial and hypoglycemic properties.

PONKORANTI (SALACIA OBLONGA/ SALACIA RETICULATA):

The common name of ponkoranti is saptrangi. These plants consist of woods and found in Srilanka and Indian forest. Diabetic treatment which we get from this forest is from its woods and stem and it is also used widely in ayurvedic therapies and in India for traditional use of this medicine for diabetes. It also is an effective and efficient weight controlling agent and anti diabetic agent. *Salacia reticulata* also proves to reduce the profile of serum lipid and also control the glycemic effect in patient with pre diabetes and who have mild hyperglycemia.

ALOE VERA AND ALOE BARBADENSIS:

Aloe is used for multiple remedies and has multiple advantages. We can extract out this plant into basic product also use as a dried juice obtained from the leaf and aloe gel. The oral use of aloe has been widely spread along side with its tropical use because it contains a glucoside of aloe emodin, cathartic anthraquinones, barbaloin. And the gel is obtained from the leaves in a portion. It also used in home remedies when we have burns, abuses. It also very effective in diabetes. There is a study in Japan which reveals the effect of aloe gel on blood sugar. After the studies there are many active ingredients extracted

out that were prove to be effective in reducing the blood glucose and glycosylated haemoglobin.

FENUGREEK (TRIGONELLA FOENUM GRAECUM):

Fenugreek is widely used all over the India and it has unpleasant taste and it is member of legume family. It is the most important constituent in Indian spices. Variety of health issues can be treated by the fenugreek like insulin resistance, inflammation, digestive problems, and diabetes. The ingredients like 4 hydroxyleucine it elevated stimulated glucose insulin release. In an animal study it has been evident that they reduce the blood glucose level in the extracted form.

GARLIC (ALLIUM SATIVUM):

Bulbous perennial herb is a allium sativum and it is 1.2 meter or 4 ft tall. Hermaphrodite flower produce by allium sativum. Allium contained the constituent that is sulfur which is important for it pungent smell and it is also important for its hypoglycemic activity due to sulfur increase the insulin release from pancreatic beta cells, raise the hepatic metabolism and insulin sparing effect. Garlic also has anti cancer, anti microbial and cardio protective properties.

CINNAMON (CINNAMOMUM):

It is produce from the genus cinnamomum. Korunda, kayu manis, dal chini and kurandu are the common name of cinnamon. In diabetes mellitus type2 it controls the blood glucose level. Methylhydroxy chalcone polymer is the active ingredient in cinnamon which mimics the insulin raises glucose metabolism and adequately decreasing blood glucose level.

INDIAN KINO (PTEROCARPUS MARSUPIUM):

Malabar kino, vijayasar, piasal, Indian kino, venkai and bijiayasal are the other names of pterocarpus marsupium. It is commonly found in hilly region of India. It can be cultivate up to 30 meters tall. Tannates is present in the pterostilbene which is constituent and obtained from wood and shows that the hypoglycemic property. Pancreatic beta cell can be regulating by the flavonoids which is a constituent of Indian kino. Indian kino also contain constituent like epicatechin which increases the insulin release and has insulinogenic property.

BITTER MELON (MOMORDICA CHARANTIA):

Bitter melon belongs to the family cucurbitaceae. It is bitter in taste and usually called as balsam pear, aampalaya, balsamina, bitter gourd and karela. It is a tropical herb and it is eatable after cooking. It has more potassium than bananas and also a very good source of vitamin c and a. It does exert reducing sugar effect that is hypoglycemic effect while elevating the uptake of glucose. It also improves release of insulin. It is an also a very good in lowering down the body triglyceride and cholesterol. The studies suggested the use of M charantia would cause the release of insulin from the pancreatic of beta cell of endocrine glands. This observation is then further monitored by daily taking M charantia juice. The compounds like 3 hydroxycucurbita-5, 23 di-o- beta glucopyranoside and 24 dien-19-al-7 are extracted out separately in another class called as saponins from M charantia. These two compounds represent prominent activity of insulin release in MIN6 beta cells at concentration of 10 and 25.

CHAMOMILE (MATRICARIA CHAMOMILLA) AND CHAMOMILE TEA:

Chamomile belongs to the family asteraceae. It is also called as chamomile. It has evidently being witness as one of the best agents for decreasing blood glucose and also

protects the risk of diabetes mellitus type2. It also has a quit significant role in protecting the destruction cause by elevated blood sugar level. Any complication which lead to diabetes mellitus can be cure by using these studies have been conducted which shows the hyperglycemic effect of chamomile. The extract of chamomile represents the blockage against aldose reductase (ALR2) enzymes. Inhibition of the assemble sorbitol in human red blood cells have been done by the component of chamomile. These components are luteolin, umbelliferone, quercetin and esculetin. If we take chamomile tea daily it could lead to the prevention of the hyperglycemia and the complication and emergencies of diabetes.

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